

ANALYSIS OF THE INCIDENCE WITH NEURALOGY OF TRIGEMINAL NERVE

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Abstract. It is important to suggest that trigeminal neuralgia (TN), which received its name in 1671, was first described in his letters in the first century of the last millennium by the healer Aretaeus from Cappadocia. He described in detail the disease, which proceeds with excruciating attacks of pain in half of the face. Trigeminal neuralgia, or trigeminal neuralgia (TN) is one of the most common facial pains (prosopalgia). According to WHO, the prevalence of TN is up to 30-50 patients per 100,000 population, and the incidence is 2-4 people per 100,000 population. The problem of TN is very relevant in the modern world. The persistent nature, high intensity of TN, resistance to traditional methods of treatment, the tendency to chronic pain lead to a deterioration in the patient's quality of life, which is manifested in sleep disturbances, a decrease in daily activity, the development of anxiety and depression. Chronic TN, difficult to treat and leading to the development of concomitant complications, often leads to temporary or permanent disability, which in turn is an economic and social problem.

Keywords: prosopalgia, Aretaeus, Maxillofacial Surgery, trigeminal neuralgia.

Purpose of the study. Study of the disease

Material and methods of the study. It is important to suggest that in the Department of Maxillofacial Surgery of the 7th City Clinical Hospital, 120 patients (85 women and 35 men) aged 10 to 75 with neuralgia of different branches of the trigeminal nerve were examined from June 2015 to May 2022. Of the 120 patients, 38 patients were operated on, 82 patients were treated with medication.

Treatment methods	General	Men	Women
Surgical	38	15	23
Medicinal	82	21	61
Right	67	26	41
Left	52	10	42
Mixed	1	0	1

Duration of the disease	men	women
Up to 1 year	5	8
From 1 to 5 years	18	38
More than 5 years	20	31

In 2020, humanity faced a pandemic of a formidable virus codenamed Covid-19, which spread throughout the world. According to WHO, the virus was first registered on December 31, 2019 in Wuhan, China. Currently, in order to obtain rapid operational scientific data on the new virus and its complications, WHO maintains close cooperation with international experts, relevant

medical institutions in various countries. According to the latest WHO data, more than 110 million people have fallen ill with this virus, the number of deaths is more than 2.2 million people. At the same time, along with the number of sick people with mild, moderate, severe course, various complications are reported (sinusitis, pneumonia, bronchitis, acute respiratory failure, pulmonary edema, sepsis, infectious toxic shock, kidney damage, liver, heart, brain). However, in the available literature we have not found any works containing a set of studies that would allow us to identify the most informative of them for assessing the condition of patients and planning complex treatment of purulent-inflammatory complications of Covid-19 in the maxillofacial region.

Branch lesions	Left side of the face	Right side of the face	men	women
First branch	1			1
Second branch	38		9	29
Third branch	22		7	15
First and second branches	4		1	3
Second and third branches	43		12	31
All branches	0	0	0	0

The purpose of the research is to study a set of clinical, laboratory and instrumental indicators based on the data obtained, to identify the most indicative tests in planning complex treatment of post-coronavirus purulent-inflammatory complications of the maxillofacial region.

Materials and Methodology

Besides that, in the clinic Happy Life Medical Center, 35 patients (23 men and 12 women) aged 34 to 89 years with purulent-inflammatory complications of the maxillofacial region after a severe form of Covid-19 with purulent-inflammatory complications localized in the maxillofacial region were examined from August 2020 to January 2021. Of the 35 patients, 30 had a history of diabetes mellitus, 2 had hypertension, 1 had cirrhosis of the liver and gastric ulcer, 1 patient had pleurisy, 1 had pyelonephritis. 22 of them came to the clinic 15 days after the onset of the disease, 6 after a month and 7 after 2 months. From the anamnesis, it was revealed that the general condition of the patients upon admission to the clinic was assessed as severe. Consciousness is clear, body temperature from 37.8 to 39.5, respiratory rate up to 25 times per minute, saturation up to 92%. On auscultation, rough breathing with wheezing was heard, heart sounds were muffled, pulse up to 90 beats per minute. The radiograph revealed signs of bilateral polysegmental pneumonia, against the background of anticoronavirus therapy, pain in the upper jaw on the 8-10th day from the onset of the Covid-19 disease. Laboratory data: from Hb-106 g g / l to 115 g / l, erythrocytes - from $3.2 \cdot 10^{12} / l$ to $4.1 \cdot 10^{12} / l$ color index - from 0.8 to 0.9; platelets - from $165.0 \cdot 10^9 / l$ to $236.0 \cdot 10^9 / l$; leukocytes - from $7.3 \cdot 10^9 / l$ to $10.2 \cdot 10^9 / l$; blood clotting start from 3 min. 15 sec to 3 min. 48 sec, end from - 4 min. 2 sec to 4 min. 56 sec;

Biochemical blood test: Total protein - from 63 to 79 g/l; glucose - from 33 to 41 mmol/l; urea - from 2.9 mmol/l to 4.6 mmol/l; creatinine - from 49 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ to 73 $\mu\text{mol/l}$; bilirubin - from 10.4 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ to 13.5 $\mu\text{mol/l}$; ALT - from 28 U/L to 41 U/L; AST - 17 U/L to 29 U/L;

Covid tests -19 positive.

The following were prescribed for the treatment course: diet #15; bed rest; oxygen therapy; baktamet 1.5 mg + sodium chloride 0.9% - 100.0, 1 time per day; ascorbic acid 5% - 10 ml intravenously by jet stream 2 times per day; dexamethasone according to the scheme; veroshpiron 1 tablet 1 time per day, acfadetrim 6 drops 2 times per day; cardiomagnyl 150 mg, 1 tablet 1 time per day; clexane 0.4 2 times per day. Against the background of the anticoronavirus therapy, patients noted the appearance of pain in the upper jaw on the 8-10th day from the beginning of treatment. Bilateral thickening of the alveolar process, swelling and hyperemia of the mucous membrane and purulent discharge from the nose were noted on the 11-14th day from the onset of Covid-19 with a severe course. All patients underwent surgical interventions in outpatient and inpatient settings (tooth extraction, opening of purulent foci, neurectomy with external and intraoral access, endoscopic revision of the paranasal sinuses, removal of the eyeball). At the time of patients seeking medical help in our clinic, the picture of the subacute stage of osteomyelitis of the upper jaw was in 19 (54.28%), chronic osteomyelitis of the upper jaw was in 14 (40%), necrosis of the eyeball and half of the face with chronic osteomyelitis of the upper jaw of the ethmoid labyrinth, the lower wall of the orbit, the main bone in 2 (5.7%), chronic osteomyelitis of the zygomatic bone in 2 (5.7%) patients. The condition of 15 patients was assessed as relatively satisfactory, of 17 - moderately severe and of 3 patients - severe. These patients were examined laboratory parameters (complete blood count, coagulogram, liver enzymes, urea, creatinine. C-reactive protein, sugar, Hepatitis B, C, HIV, Wasserman reaction). Instrumental - MSCT of the skull of the upper and lower jaw, orthopantomogram, morphological study were carried out.

As a result of the study, it was established that in patients with a subacute stage of osteomyelitis, mobility of all teeth of the upper jaw, swelling and hyperemia of the gums on both sides of the alveolar process, the presence of purulent discharge from the nose with a foul odor on the affected side, especially in patients suffering from diabetes mellitus, were noted. From the side of laboratory tests, an increase in the level of leukocytes to 10.8-10.9, ESR to 35 mm per hour, fibrinogen concentration to 435 mg-l and platelets 453×10.9 mg-l, C-reactive protein 485 mg/l and sugar up to 26.6 mg/mol, shortening of blood clotting time to 18 seconds were noted.

In chronic osteomyelitis, elevated fibrinogen, C-reactive protein, platelets, leukocytes and ESR slightly exceeded the normal values. In 2 patients with necrosis of the eyeball and chronic osteomyelitis of the zygomatic bone, an increase in blood sugar concentration to 20 m1mmol and C-reactive protein to 423 were noted.

During radiographic examination, 19 patients showed signs of osteomyelitis of the upper jaw with a predominant lesion of the alveolar process at the level of incisors, premolars and molars, 12 patients showed signs of osteomyelitis of the upper jaw with inflammation in the ethmoid labyrinth on the affected side, curvature of the nasal septum.

In 1 patient with necrosis of the eyeball and half of the face, signs of chronic osteomyelitis of the upper jaw, ethmoid labyrinth and the lower wall of the orbit, and the greater wing of the sphenoid bone were noted. One patient had bilateral chronic osteomyelitis of the maxilla with damage to the paranasal sinuses and ethmoid labyrinth and the bone of the base of the skull. In two patients with chronic osteomyelitis of the zygomatic bone, a focus of bone rarefaction was noted in the area of the body of the zygomatic bone.

Morphological studies have shown signs of inflammation in bone and soft tissue. Here is an example:

Patient: G.S., 1984	
Date and time of admission:	20.11.2020 16:02
Date and time of issue:	26.11.2020 18:20
Identification number:	28256/20

DESCRIPTION OF MACROMATERIAL

Multiple fragments of bone tissue, brown in color, soft in consistency, with a total size of 1.5 x 1 cm.

Prepared: 4 cassettes and 4 slides. A) Soft tissue; B, C, D) Bone tissue.

MICROSCOPIC DESCRIPTION

A. The soft tissue surface is lined with high multi-row ciliated epithelium with foci of proliferation. The stroma is represented by connective tissue with myxoid edema, foci of dense inflammatory, predominantly lymphocytic infiltration with an admixture of plasma cells.

B, C, D. Small fragments of bone tissue with pronounced dystrophic, necrotic or destructive changes. Interosseous tissue with large foci of necrosis of lymphoplasmacytic infiltration with an admixture of leukocytes.

CONCLUSION

Chronic osteomyelitis with areas of sequestration, inflammation of adjacent soft tissues. On the day of the patient's visit with a subacute stage of osteomyelitis of the upper jaw, the

destroyed teeth were removed with perforation of the maxillary sinus floor for free evacuation of purulent discharge. In the absence of destroyed teeth, 6 patients underwent catheterization of the maxillary sinus with subsequent irrigation of the sinuses with antiseptics (chlorhexidine, furacilin, decasan, betadine). All 19 patients after examination by specialists were prescribed a course of outpatient treatment: thymalin 1.0 intramuscularly, vitamin therapy, serrata 2 tablets 3 times a day for a month, adaptogens, prescriptions of a pulmonologist, cardiologist, endocrinologist, observation by a doctor at the place of residence. Observations carried out over 2 months showed the effectiveness of the complex treatment, since the phenomena of purulent-inflammatory processes were quickly stopped.

It is important to suggest that in 16 patients with chronic osteomyelitis, 6 had an increase in blood sugar to 26 m-mol, 1 patient had a decrease in the concentration of platelets in the blood to $114 \cdot 10^9/l$. This group of patients after correction of sugar and blood platelets were operated under intubation anesthesia together with ENT specialists. In this case, necrotic tissue in the maxillary sinus, sequesters in the alveolar process of half of the upper jaw, the lower part of the anterior and lateral wall of the maxillary sinus and a complete absence of the inner wall of the maxillary sinus were found. Necrotic tissue and sequesters with mobile and destroyed teeth were removed, hemostasis. A distinctive feature of post-covid osteomyelitis of the upper jaw is the presence of large sequesters and jagged edges of sequesters with the smell of acetone with simultaneous damage to the paranasal sinuses. ENT specialists performed revision of the ethmoid labyrinth, frontal and main sinuses, anterior and middle sections of the ethmoid labyrinth using an endoscopic apparatus. After placing the anastomosis on the inferior nasal passage, the sinuses were tamponed with levomecol or betadine ointment and the wound was sutured with silk sutures. In the postoperative period, patients were prescribed a course of complex treatment: ceftriaxone 1.0 2 times a day intramuscularly. Tivortin 100.0 intravenously by drip, painkillers, desensitizing, tonic drugs, drugs that lower blood sugar levels. Tampons from the sinuses were removed on the 2nd day.

Considering the duration of the disease and the decrease in the immunobiological reactivity of the body, the sutures were removed on the 12th-14th day after the operation. In 4 patients with chronic osteomyelitis and in 2 with chronic osteomyelitis of the zygomatic bone, residual effects of Covid-19 were detected during MSCT of the chest, which were referred to a doctor at the place of residence for further treatment. 3 patients with a serious condition were referred for further examination and treatment to an ophthalmologist and a neurosurgeon.

During endoscopic surgery of the maxillary sinuses and ethmoid labyrinth, necrotic changes in the walls of the sinuses with purulent foci and in places hypertrophy and hyperemia of the mucous membranes were noted in patients, with the presence of small sequesters with narrowing of the natural openings of the sinuses, curvature of the nasal septum, hypertrophy and hyperemia of the nasal turbinates.

By summarizing it can be suggested that in the subacute stage of osteomyelitis, early tooth extraction and perforation of the maxillary sinus or catheterization of the maxillary sinus followed by irrigation with antiseptics and complex therapy contribute to a rapid reduction in the symptoms of the inflammatory process and an improvement in the general condition of patients. In chronic osteomyelitis, surgical intervention performed jointly with ENT specialists using endoscopic technology and complex treatment allows to get a good cosmetic and functional result.

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